

Brief Discussion about the Management of Diabetes Mellitus and its complication

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Abstract

An extremely common illness is diabetes mellitus commonly referred to as a chronic medical condition characterized by high levels of blood sugar (glucose). These difficulties include an increasing incidence of the condition in both urban and rural regions, a lack of knowledge about the condition, a lack of healthcare resources, expensive treatment options, good glycemic control, and an increase in diabetes complications. Because of its frequent usage and delivery, insulin treatment can be more costing on patients. The primary contributors to the pandemic include type 2 diabetes, which is caused by genetics, the environment, obesity, and sedentary lifestyles. Numerous treatment plans, including those involving gene therapy, stem cell therapy, medical nutrition therapy, and lifestyle changes, are demonstrating encouraging outcomes. Optimizing glycemic control, maintaining patient compliance, resolving safety and ethical issues, and establishing efficient delivery methods are among the difficulties associated with putting these strategies into practice. The significance of a thorough strategy for managing diabetes, including dietary adjustments, pharmaceutical therapies, and the enhancement of novel therapeutic modalities. It also emphasizes the necessity of gaining a deeper comprehension of the biology of diabetes and of treating patients according to their unique characteristics and stage of the illness. The article's overall gives the information about the risk factors and the management of diabetes mellitus.

Keywords Diabetes mellitus, Insulin, Gene therapy, Stem cell therapy.

Introduction Diabetes mellitus (DM), often known as hyperglycemia is characterized by excessive blood sugar levels. Diabetes is very common chronic disease that occurs when the pancreas is not able to produce enough insulin or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin it produces. The World Health Organisation (WHO) describes DM as an epidemic that is very deadly and crippling. 90% of the 425 million persons with diabetes who have been diagnosed globally have type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and that number is expected to rise to 629 million by 2045 [1]. In 2019, 1.5 million direct deaths were caused by diabetes and 48% of these deaths were occurred due to diabetes before the age of 70 years [2]. Both the hormones insulin and glucagon are released by the pancreas. The beta (β) cells in the islets of Langerhans release insulin, whereas the alpha (α) cells release glucagon. Insulin lowers blood sugar levels by promoting glycogenesis and delivering glucose to the muscles, liver, and adipose tissue, while alpha (α) cells play a significant role in managing blood glucose by generating glucagon, which raises blood glucose levels by speeding glycogenolysis, neural tissue and erythrocytes do not require insulin to use glucose [3,4]. Recently the main therapeutic agents for T2DM are insulin-like agents and oral administration of anti diabetic agents. However these agents play a vital role of the treatment of T2DM but having a lots of side effects [5,6]. Insulin has been the focus of treatment of uncontrolled insulin deficiency since its invention [7]. However, due to severe beta cell deficiency, injection of exogenous insulin is essential for survival. Despite the progress that has been made in understanding the etiology, effects, and persistence of DM, including advances in the development of insulin and its analogues, ensuring strict blood glucose modulation without negative side effects such as hypoglycemia and weight gain is still a major problem [8,9,10].

All treatment guidelines emphasize the benefits of early, effective, and sustained glycemic control to delay the onset and reduce the severity of complications. Given the variable and progressive nature of type 2 diabetes, most guidelines advocate an individualized treatment approach supported and accompanied by lifestyle intervention measures, particularly diet, exercise, weight control, and healthy lifestyle advice [11-14].

Goals of Treatment

The major goals of treating diabetes are to avoid early decompensation, prevent or postpone the onset of late disease complications, decrease mortality, and preserve a high quality of life [15]. The primary goal is to keep blood sugar levels within the desired range. Regarding chronic complications of the disease, it is very understandable that good glycemic control can reduce the incidence of microvascular complications (retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy) whereas good glycemic control does not seem to be so crucial for the prevention of macrovascular complications (ischemic heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, peripheral arteriopathy)[16,17]. In this view, treatment of hyperglycemia should be considered as part of an essential approach to the combined risk factors in these patients (arterial hypertension [AHT], dyslipidemia, smoking). Thus, treatment aimed at optimal glycemic control and neglecting other cardiovascular risk factors is not very useful [18,19]. In elderly patients or those with a very limited life expectancy, it is not compulsory to achieve this therapeutic goal, as this carries a high risk of severe hypoglycemia. Regarding the target lipid profile and blood pressure, it should be remembered that ischemic heart disease is the major cause of mortality in diabetics [20,21] and that the cardiovascular risk of diabetics is similar to that of nondiabetics who already have ischemic heart disease[22].

It's worth noting that treatment goals are individualized and may vary depending on factors such as age, overall health, duration of diabetes, and presence of other medical conditions. It is important for individuals with diabetes to work closely with their healthcare team to develop a personalized treatment plan and set appropriate goals.

Objective of study The objective of the Study is to discussion about the management of Diabetes Mellitus and its complication.

Review of Literature This is a review based paper so reviews have discussed through out the paper.

Methodology The literature search for this narrative review was conducted utilising a variety of search engines, including Scopus, Google Scholar, Pubmed/Medline, and Web of Science databases, to find published papers on current advancements in the management of DM. Diabetes mellitus, hyperglycemia, DM management, T2DM, stem cell therapy in diabetes, gene therapy in DM management and current treatment, etc. are among the keywords and subject titles used. The titles and abstracts of the search results were methodically vetted to identify publications that were appropriate for fulltext viewing. Original research and review articles published between 1993 and 2023 (in English) were included. Thesis and unpublished articles were eliminated. The chosen papers' legitimacy was confirmed by all of the authors.

Analysis Risk factors of diabetes

There are several risk factors associated with the development of diabetes mellitus. These factors increase the likelihood of developing the condition. The risk of T2DM increases with age which is due to the deficiency of insulin secretion which develop with age, and growing insulin resistance caused by a change in body composition[23]. The main risk factors for diabetes include but not limited to age; weight; family, history of diabetes; smoking and race/ethnicity [24,25]. While T1DM usually occurs in young people, T2DM is a disease of the adult. The risk for T2DM increases with age, which is due to deficient insulin secretion developing with age and increasing insulin resistance due to altered body composition[26]. An increase in body weight leading to obesity is closely associated with diabetes and is called diabetes. This is because an increase in body weight leads to increased insulin resistance [27].

Diabetic retinopathy

Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) plays a key role in the development of diabetic retinopathy [28]. Patients with proliferative diabetic retinopathy have high levels of VEGF, which stimulates angiogenesis in the retina [29,30]. According to clinical studies, intraocular injections of anti-VEGF antibodies are superior to conventional laser treatment for treating diabetic macular edema in patients [31]. In Japan, two medications (ranibizumab or aflibercept) have received clinical approval for the treatment of diabetic macular edema.

Renin-angiotensin system (RAS) inhibitors may significantly lower the incidence of diabetic retinopathy, according to a number of studies. The angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor lisinopril reduced the evolution of diabetic

retinopathy in normotensive type 1 diabetes patients without albuminuria, according to the EURODIAB Controlled Trial of Lisinopril in Insulin-Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (EUCLID) study [32]. The United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) 69 research, however, demonstrated that ACE inhibitors' effects were not superior to β blockers [33]. According to the Diabetic Retinopathy Candesartan Trials Prevent and Project (DIRECT) 1 research, people with type 1 diabetes likely to have a lower incidence of diabetic retinopathy while using the angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB) candesartan. However, these modifications were not statistically significant [34]. Candesartan has been shown to reduce the evolution of diabetic retinopathy in the Diabetic Retinopathy Candesartan Trials Prevent and Project (DIRECT) 2 research [35]. In the Fenofibrate Intervention and Event Lowering in Diabetes (FIELD) research, it was also shown that fenofibrate management of hyperlipidemia reduced the frequency of patients with type 2 diabetes and diabetic retinopathy who needed laser therapy [36].

Diabetic kidney disease

Intensive glycemc management decreased the incidence of microalbuminuria in both type 1 and type 2 diabetes with normoalbuminuria, according to the DCCT the Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT) research and the UKPDS studies [8,37]. Additionally, the Action in Diabetes and Vascular Disease: PreterAx and DiamicroNMR

Controlled Evaluation (ADVANCE) experiment found that regardless of the severity of DKD, individuals with diabetes should have blood pressure management that is less than 130/80 mmHg [38]. The Japanese Society of Hypertension concurs with this proposal and suggests that the aim that the recommended blood pressure is less than 130/80 mmHg [39]. However, the Cardiovascular Risk Reduction Programme in Diabetes (ACCORD) experiment has shown that diligent regulation of blood pressure (systolic pressure less than 120 mmHg) did not reduce CVD, rather exacerbated side effects as hypotension and an elevated serum creatinine [40].

RAS inhibitors reduce glomerular hypertension, which has renoprotective benefits. The effectiveness of RAS inhibitors in overt diabetic nephropathy has been proven by two significant trials [41,42]. The composite primary outcome for both studies was the doubling of serum creatinine as well as the progression to end-stage renal disease and death. The Reduction in Endpoints in NIDDM with the Angiotensin Antagonist Losartan (RENAAL) trial found that patients with type 2 diabetes and overt diabetic nephropathy experienced fewer primary endpoints when taking ARB losartan compared to the placebo group, but there was no statistically significant difference in CVD incidence [41].

In tests on animals, ACE inhibitor blood pressure lowering increased oxygenation and nerve transmission [43]. Similar to this, ACE inhibitor therapy enhanced the speed of nerve transmission in both the motor and sensory systems in diabetic individuals [44]. It is therefore likely that blood pressure lowering with an ACE inhibitor enhances nerve conduction but does not significantly halt the development of diabetic neuropathy.

Diabetic Neuropathy

The most prevalent chronic consequence of diabetes is diabetic neuropathy [45]. The most typical kind is chronic, symmetrical peripheral polyneuropathy. A high incidence of diabetic neuropathy is linked to the length of diabetes and levels of glycated hemoglobin [46]. Another risk factor for diabetic neuropathy is hypertension [47]. Painful polyneuropathy must be treated with pharmacological symptomatic treatments [47]. For symptom management, tricyclic antidepressants, anticonvulsants (pregabalin), and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (duloxetine) are advised [48,49]. In Japan, epalrestat, an inhibitor of aldose reductase, is authorised for the treatment of diabetic neuropathy.

Epalrestat appeared to lessen the neurological manifestations of diabetic neuropathy and enhance neural conduction velocity, according to a randomised control experiment [50]. The effectiveness, nevertheless, was only applicable to the early stages of neuropathy.

Clinical studies have furthermore demonstrated that the antioxidant lipoic acid reduces neural symptoms in diabetic and neuropathy patients but does not enhance neural conduction [51,52]. Due to increased sympathetic nerve activity at night, patients with diabetes and autonomic neuropathy also show a lack of the typical overnight drop in blood pressure [53]. Thus, the occurrence of diabetic autonomic neuropathy is frequently linked to a non-dipper pattern of blood pressure throughout the development of diabetes [54]

As a macro-vascular complication, cardiovascular disease (CVD)

The major CV diseases (CVDs) associated with T2DM include ischemic heart disease, heart failure (HF), stroke, coronary artery disease (CAD), and

peripheral artery disease, and these complications can result in death for at least 50% of patients with T2DM [55]. Before 2016, there was a 14.3 to 46.9% range in the prevalence of all CVDs in T2DM[56], according to a meta-analysis for the years 2007 to 2017 [55]. According to reports, there were 13 nations with a weighted prevalence of CVD of 34.8%, but there was a considerable variation between them, varying from 18.0% in Saudi Arabia to 56.5% in Israel [57].

Class	Genes	Main Function
Genes modulating homeostasis of glucose	GLUTs	Involved in the re-absorption of filtered glucose from the kidney into the bloodstream
	SGLTs	Partake profoundly in muscle and hepatic glucose fluxes
	FGFs	Functions significantly in the homeostasis of glucose
	SIRT6	Connected with an expression of GLUTs and increased glycolysis
Genes enhancing the secretion of insulin and/or sensitivity	GLP-1 and its analogs/agonists	Boost the survival of beta-cell, provoke the expression of the insulin gene, and synthesis
	GPGRs and their agonists	Enhances the secretion of insulin and GLP-1
	CTB-APSL	Enhances secretion of insulin and insulin resistance
	IKK E, TBK1	Linked with diminution in weight, insulin resistance, fatty liver as well as inflammation
Genes attenuating diabetic induced complications	IL-1b	Linked with inflammation and b-cell failure
	ADPN	Attenuates diabetic nephropathy
	TGF-a	Has a function in DKD linked with nephron reduction
	NLRP3	Attenuates diabetic cardiomyopathy
	CDKN2A/2B	connected with modulation of T-cell phenotype and chronic inflammation
	HSP70	Connected with bioenergetics of mitochondrion and diabetic sensory neuropathy
	MicroRNAs	Implicated in the modulation of diabetic microvasculature

Fasting blood glucose levels below 7mol/L were associated with an increased risk of coronary heart disease, according to a meta-analysis of 102 prospective studies [58]. A higher risk of CVD has also been linked to poor glucose tolerance and rising HbA1c levels (> 5.7%), according to research [59]. An elevated blood glucose level increases the risk of CVD and all-cause mortality in both the general population and in patients with atherosclerotic CVD [60]. Improved CVD prevention in T2DM may result from personalised glycemic control. This section focuses on contemporary elements of T2DM management on an individual basis.

A study found that regardless of baseline systolic blood pressure, evaluating blood pressures as low as 120 mm Hg and 70 mm Hg could reduce mortality, macrovascular, and microvascular events. The presence of hypertension in patients with T2DM significantly increases the risk of CVD development [61]. Therefore, decreasing blood pressure lowers CVD events and microvascular complications and improves CVD outcomes in both T2DM patients and non-T2DM patients [62].

Non-Pharmacological Treatment

Gene Therapy

Currently, gene manipulation includes gene regulation and editing in addition to the insertion of new genes [63,64]. Gene therapy can also be explained as a method of introduction of a gene or gene manipulation within a cell as a curative regimen in the treatment of disease[65]. Because the target for genetic engineering comes from the receiver of the transplant and may represent an endless supply of autologous cells, ectopic expression of genes is a commonly utilised approach that avoids the need for immunosuppressive therapies. Continuous monitoring of glucose levels, regulated transcription and translation of pro-insulin, regulated processing of pro-insulin to mature insulin, regulated storage of mature insulin, and regulated secretion of mature insulin to a stimulus, such as glucose, are all significant characteristics of -cells that are crucial in the regulation of blood sugar levels[66,67]. Liposomes carrying DNA have negligible positive charges, which enhances their ability to connect with target cells and, as a result, the effectiveness of transfection [68]. The dissociated islets might not operate if their shape is not maintained. Gene transfer into the cell is conceivable, however electroporation cannot effectively integrate DNA into the host genome [69]. Table 1 explains Promising targets that can be employed for T2DM gene therapy.

Legend: HSP70 = heat shock protein 70; NLRP3 = nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-like receptor protein 3; SGLTs = sodium-glucose co-transporters; GLUTs, glucosetransporters; SIRT6=Sirtuin 6; FGFs = fibroblast growth factors; GPGRs = G protein-coupled receptors; GLP-1= glycogen-like peptide 1; ADPN = adiponectin; CTB APSL = cholera toxinB subunit and active peptide from shark liver; TGF-a = transforming growth factor-alpha; DKD = diabetic kidney disease [70].

Steam Cell Therapy

Monocytes and macrophages may play a major role in these ongoing inflammatory processes and insulin resistance in T2DM patients, according to research [71].In the management of DM, stem cell investigation has become a promising approach [72]. The goal of the stem cell DM treatment is to replace damaged or dysfunctional pancreatic cells by using pluripotent or multipotent stem cells. The capacity of several types of stem cells, such as induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), embryonic stem cells (ESCs), and adult stem cells, to make substitute beta cells or restore the physiological function of the beta cell has been used in this procedure.[73].A modest amount of pancreatic tissue, if accessible, has been shown in studies using animal models to be able to restore the ideal pancreatic beta-cell mass[74].This occurs as a result of the differentiated beta cells from the pancreatic duct going through replication and dedifferentiation, which results in the generation of pluri-potent cells that then produce more beta cells. Additional research revealed that similar ductal cell populations might be grown in vitro and programmed to form clusters that synthesize insulin [75,76].A cutting-edge technique called stem cell educator treatment is intended to regulate or correct immunological dysfunctions. The procedure involves drawing blood from the patient's circulation using a closed-loop system, separating lymphocytes from the whole blood, cocultivating them with adherent cord blood-derived multi-potent stem cells (CB-SCs), and injecting the educated lymphocytes into the patient's circulation—but not the CBSCs [77].Furthermore, mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) and haemopoietic adult stem cells (HSCs) have the capacity to trans differentiate into a variety of cell lineages, including those of the gastrointestinal system, liver, and lung[78].An experiment with autologous HSCs demonstrated an improvement in T1DM and T2DM[79,80].These studies offer prospective results for using autologous HSCs to treat diabetes mellitus.

Nutrition Therapy

Medical nutrition therapy (MNT) is a "nutrition-based treatment provided by a registered dietitian nutritionist." It comprises nutrition diagnosis and therapeutic and professional counseling services that aid in the management of DM. MNT is a critical aspect of diabetes education and management. Recommendations on MNT by international collaborative groups for diabetes management have attempted to reform and provide courses for adverse nutritional transition.[81,82].According to the Institute of Medicine, low-CHO diets currently used traditionally for the treatment of GDM have shown to be safe. Pregnant women need at least 175 g of CHO per day[83].MNT has also been shown to be essential in the treatment of various forms of diabetes, and as a result, it has had a substantial influence on patients, particularly women and babies[84].

For the treatment of oxidative stress in T2DM patients, a range of antioxidants, including vitamins, supplements, active ingredients derived from plants, and medications having antioxidant activities, have been employed. Carotene, vitamin C, and vitamin E are the best supplements for preventing oxidative stress and its side effects[85].Moreover, the changes indicate that inflammation plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of T2DM and its complications [86,87].Adipose tissue, pancreatic islets, the liver, the vasculature, and circulating leukocytes are particularly affected by T2DM, as are the numbers and states of activation of various leukocyte populations, enhanced apoptosis, and tissue fibrosis[88,89].Evidence suggests that MNT may be an effective, easily accessible, and inexpensive treatment method and might be a crucial tool for DM management and prevention[90].

Life Style Modification in Diabetes

Lifestyle modification plays a crucial role in the management of diabetes mellitus. It involves adopting healthy habits and making positive changes to your daily routine to help control blood sugar levels and prevent complications associated with diabetes. Among the suggested lifestyle changes are an increase in physical activity, a decrease in sedentary behaviour, and healthy eating. Depending on the patient's condition, the best exercise may change. The level of plasma glucose is lowered as a result of exercise. It is advised that diabetes patients consume lots of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains; select nonfat dairy products and lean meats; and minimize items that are heavy in sugar and fat. Other lifestyle modifications include giving up smoking and

drinking less alcohol [91,92].Chronic stress can impact blood sugar levels and overall health. Find healthy ways to manage stress, such as engaging in relaxation techniques (e.g., deep breathing, meditation, yoga), pursuing hobbies, spending time with loved ones, or seeking professional support if needed. Prioritizing self-care and maintaining a healthy work-life balance are also essential. To increase adherence to the lifestyle modifications, web- or internet-based programs have been used. These online techniques offer a practical means of facilitating diabetic self-management [93].

Pharmacological Treatment

Those agents which are used in the treatment of diabetes are called anti-diabetic agents. The goal of therapy is to eliminate the precipitating factor while also administering large doses of daily insulin [94].Long-term safety is crucial since a glucose-lowering medication may be needed for decades. Accessibility and adherence will be significantly impacted by administration ease, tolerability, and cost. It is often difficult to place a new drug inside a therapy algorithm: Despite the best positioning versus disease pathophysiology, initial caution frequently delays use of a novel drug until old agents have been exhausted [95,96].

Classes of drugs & Dose [mg/day]	Mode of action	Limitation, Caution
Oral		
Biguanide Metformin (IR, SR/XR formulations) [500–3000]	Counter insulin resistance ↓ Hepatic glucose output ↑ Glucose uptake and cycling	Check renal function. Interrupt if using contrast media. Avoid in renal or liver impairment, or any hypoxemic state and history of lactic acidosis
Sulfonylureas Glibenclamide [2.5-20] Gliclazide [40-320] Gliclazide MR* [30-100] Glimepiride [1-6] Glipizide [2.5-20] Tolbutamide [500-3000]	Initiate and potentiate insulin secretion (effect lasts 6–24 h depending on agent and dose)	Initial efficacy may wear-off after 6–12 months in some patients. Avoid in renal or liver impairment depending on agent. Note risk of hypoglycemia.
Meglitinides Nateglinide [60-540] Repaglinide [0.5-16]	Initiate and potentiate insulin secretion (rapid effect, typically lasts <6 h)	Avoid in liver impairment. Take with main meals.
DPP-4 inhibitors Alogliptin [6.25-25] Linagliptin [5] Saxagliptin [2.5-5] Sitagliptin [25-100] Vildagliptin [50-100]	Prolong circulating half-lives of some in cretin hormones such as GLP-1	Discontinue if acute pancreatitis. Dose adjustment in renal impairment except linagliptin.
Thiazolidinedione Pioglitazone [15-45]	↑ Insulin sensitivity mainly via activation of PPARγ	Slow onset of action, risk of oedema. Increased risk of heart failure and bone fractures.
SGLT2 inhibitors Canagliflozin [100-300] Dapagliflozin [5-10] Empagliflozin [10-25]	Inhibit renal SGLT2 to eliminate glucose via urine.	Check for adequate renal function and hydration. Glucosuric effect: risk of gen and urinary infections.
Alpha-glucosidase inhibitors Acarbose [50-600]	Slow carbohydrate digestion by competitive inhibition of intestinal glucosidases.	Avoid if gastrointestinal disorders. Side effect of flatulence.
Subcutaneous injection		
GLP-1 receptor agonists Dulaglutide [0.75-1.5QW] Exenatide BD [5-10ug] Exenatide QW [2QW] Liraglutide [0.6-1.8OD] Lixisenatide [10-20ugOD]	Activate GLP-1 receptors to potentiate prandial insulin secretion, ↓ prandial glucagon secretion, delay gastric emptying and exert satiety effect.	Initial nausea, titrate as appropriate. Avoid in severe renal impairment. Discontinue if acute pancreatitis. Can reduce blood pressure: evidence of reduced CV risk.
Insulin		
Ultra-rapid acting: Fiasp Rapid-acting:	↓ hepatic glucose output ↑ peripheral glucose uptake ↑ glucose metabolism	Select regimen consistent with patient lifestyle and needs. Glucose monitoring required.
Aspart, Glulisine, Lispro Short-acting: Actrapid, Humulin S, Insuman Rapid Intermediate: Insulatard, Humulin I Long-acting: Degludec, Detemir, Glargine Biphasic (pre-mixed): Humalog, Humulin M3, Novomix [For basal sc injections usually start at 0.1 or 0.2 units/kg body weight daily (i.e.10 or 20 units per day for a person weighing 100 kg). Titrate up dose to achieve target glycaemic control.]	↓ lipolysis ↑ lipogenesis ↑ protein anabolism	Appropriate lifestyle adjustments. Note high risk of hypoglycemia.

Based on ADA/EASD position statement [97].

This table is based on and updated from reference [98].

Conclusion Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a significant public health challenge with a rising prevalence that is expected to continue for decades. DM is a serious complication that requires urgent attention. While there is no permanent cure, various treatment options are showing promise. However, challenges remain, and a comprehensive approach combining pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions is necessary to achieve early and sustained glycemic control and minimize associated risks. Public policies and healthcare infrastructure are crucial elements in effectively managing DM.

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